

1 **A molecular basis for CDK4/6 inhibition in HCC.**

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7 HCC (hepatocellular or liver cancer) is a major cause of cancer death globally and is caused or enhanced
8 by infectious sources like Hepatitis B and C as well non-infectious sources like fatty and alcoholic liver
9 disease. We measured total transcription in humans with HCC using the normal liver as a reference
10 transcriptome to identify the most genes most abundantly expressed in the tumor. We identified activation
11 of cyclin dependent kinase *CDK4* in human HCC. The data were supportive at the basic and translational
12 level of using CDK4/6 inhibitors as adjunctive treatments in hepatocellular carcinoma, functioning in
13 adjunct as a multi-drug chemotherapy to reduce resistance while targeting a cancer vulnerability.

14 Citations

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1. Bollard J, Miguela V, Ruiz de Galarreta M, Venkatesh A, Bian CB, Roberto MP, Tovar V, Sia D, Molina-Sánchez P, Nguyen CB, Nakagawa S, Llovet JM, Hoshida Y, Lujambio A. Palbociclib (PD-0332991), a selective CDK4/6 inhibitor, restricts tumour growth in preclinical models of hepatocellular carcinoma. Gut. 2017 Jul;66(7):1286-1296. doi: 10.1136/gutjnl-2016-312268. Epub 2016 Nov 14. PMID: 27849562; PMCID: PMC5512174.